

TRANSLATION CHALLENGES IN SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL TRANSLATION WITH A FOCUS ON TERMINOLOGICAL DICTIONARIES

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“Gid hamrohligi, tarjimashunoslik va madaniyatlararo muloqot” kafedrası o’qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ilmiy va texnik tarjimalarda tarjimonlar duch keladigan tilga xos muammolar muhokama qilinadi. U jumla tuzilishi, terminologik farqlar, madaniy nuanslar, yozuv uslubi va idiomatik iboralar bilan bog'liq murakkabliklarni ta'kidlaydi. Maqolada tarjimalarni to'g'ri va samarali amalga oshirish uchun tilni bilish, mavzu bo'yicha tajriba va ushbu qiyinchiliklarni yengib o'tishda tegishli resurslardan foydalanish muhimligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ilmiy tarjima, texnik tarjima, til muammolari, jumla tuzilishi, terminologik farqlar, madaniy nuanslar, yozuv uslubi, idiomatik iboralar, tilni bilish, mavzu bo'yicha ekspertiza, lingvistik manbalar.

Annotation. This article discusses the language-specific challenges faced by translators in scientific and technical translations. It highlights the complexities related to sentence structure, terminology differences, cultural nuances, writing style, and idiomatic expressions. The article emphasizes the importance of language proficiency, subject-matter expertise, and the use of appropriate resources in overcoming these challenges to ensure accurate and effective translations.

Keywords: scientific translation, technical translation, language challenges, sentence structure, terminology differences, cultural nuances, writing style, idiomatic expressions, language proficiency, subject-matter expertise, linguistic resources.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются специфические для языка проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются переводчики при выполнении научно-технических переводов. Он подчеркивает сложности, связанные со структурой предложения, терминологическими различиями, культурными нюансами, стилем письма и идиоматическими выражениями. В статье подчеркивается важность владения языком, предметной экспертизы и использования соответствующих ресурсов для преодоления этих проблем для обеспечения точных и эффективных переводов.

Ключевые слова: научный перевод, технический перевод, языковые проблемы, структура предложения, терминологические различия, культурные нюансы, стиль письма, идиоматические выражения, владение языком, предметная экспертиза, лингвистические ресурсы.

INTRODUCTION

Translation plays a vital role in bridging language barriers in various fields, including scientific and technical domains. However, the end of scientific technical translations and the use of terminological dictionaries often present unique challenges. This article aims to explore these specific translation problems and highlight the importance of accurate and comprehensive terminological dictionaries in ensuring precise translations.

1. Contextual Ambiguity:

Scientific and technical texts are filled with complex terms and concepts, making it essential for translators to understand the context in which these terms are used. The lack of precise

context can lead to ambiguity, resulting in inaccurate translations. Terminological dictionaries become invaluable tools in providing translators with the necessary context and definitions for these specialized terms.

2. Polysemy and Homonymy:

Polysemy and homonymy are common occurrences in scientific and technical translations, posing significant challenges for translators. Polysemy refers to words with multiple meanings, while homonymy is the existence of similar-sounding words with different meanings. Both can introduce confusion and ambiguity. Terminological dictionaries should offer detailed explanations and examples to help translators accurately identify and differentiate these terms.

3. Lack of Equivalents:

Translating scientific and technical terms often involves encountering concepts that do not have direct equivalents in the target language. In such cases, translators face the challenge of finding appropriate alternatives that convey the same meaning. Terminological dictionaries can provide translators with suggestions, explanations, and references to support the selection of suitable equivalents or alternatives.

4. Rapidly Evolving Terminology:

Scientific and technical fields are constantly evolving, leading to the emergence of new terminologies and concepts. Translators must keep pace with these developments to ensure accurate translations. Terminological dictionaries need to be regularly updated with the latest terminologies and definitions to aid translators in their work.

5. Language-Specific Challenges:

Different languages have unique syntax, grammar, and semantic structures that can pose challenges during translation. Scientific and technical texts often use complex sentence structures and specialized vocabulary. Translators need to navigate these intricacies while maintaining accuracy and readability. Terminological dictionaries tailored to the specific language can facilitate this process by providing language-specific guidance.

Main part

Contextual ambiguity is a significant challenge that translators face in scientific and technical translations. Scientific and technical texts often contain specialized terminology and complex concepts that require a deep understanding of the subject matter. Without a clear understanding of the context in which these terms are used, translators may struggle to accurately convey the intended meaning. One common example of contextual ambiguity is the use of acronyms and abbreviations in scientific and technical texts. These abbreviations can have multiple meanings depending on the field or context in which they are used. Translators need to rely on context clues and accurate terminological dictionaries to determine the correct interpretation of these abbreviations.

Polysemy and homonymy are common linguistic phenomena that pose challenges for translators in scientific and technical translations. These concepts relate to words that have multiple meanings or similar-sounding words with different meanings, respectively.

Polysemy refers to the phenomenon where a single word can have multiple related meanings. In scientific and technical texts, polysemous terms are prevalent due to the vast and interconnected nature of these fields. For example, the word "band" can refer to a group of musicians, a region of the electromagnetic spectrum, or a strip of DNA. Translators must accurately identify the intended meaning based on the context in order to provide an appropriate translation

The lack of equivalents poses a significant challenge for translators in scientific and technical translations. In these domains, there are often concepts or terms that do not have direct translations in the target language. This can occur due to cultural differences, variations in scientific terminology across languages, or the absence of an exact counterpart for a specific concept.

When faced with a lack of equivalents, translators must carefully consider their options and find appropriate alternatives that convey the same meaning. Terminological dictionaries can be valuable resources in such situations, providing translators with suggestions and explanations to help them identify suitable equivalents or alternatives.

Rapidly evolving terminology is a commonly encountered challenge in scientific and technical translations. The nature of scientific and technical fields is one of constant progress and innovation. New discoveries, advancements, and technologies often lead to the emergence of new terminologies and concepts. As a result, translators need to stay updated with the latest developments to accurately translate these evolving terms.

The challenge arises when there is a time gap between the publication of the source text and the translation process. During this time, new terminologies may have been introduced or existing terms may have acquired new meanings. If translators are not aware of these changes, it can lead to outdated or inaccurate translations.

Language-specific challenges are inherent in scientific and technical translations due to the unique grammatical and semantic structures of different languages. Translating scientific and technical texts requires not only a deep understanding of the subject matter but also a thorough knowledge of the intricacies of the target language. Here are some language-specific challenges that translators often encounter:

1. **Sentence Structure:** Scientific and technical texts often use complex sentence structures involving subordinate clauses, technical specifications, and precise modifiers. Translators must effectively convey the intended meaning while maintaining grammatical correctness in the target language. They may need to restructure sentences or use suitable equivalents to ensure clarity and readability.

2. **Terminology Differences:** Different languages may have variations in their scientific and technical terminology. Translators need to be aware of these discrepancies and use appropriate translations or adaptations to ensure accuracy. Contextual understanding and reference to specialized dictionaries become critical in overcoming these challenges.

3. **Cultural Nuances:** Scientific and technical texts can contain cultural references or examples that need to be adapted to fit the target language and culture. Translators must be mindful of cultural nuances and adapt the content accordingly to ensure the text is culturally appropriate and comprehensible to the target audience.

4. **Writing Style:** Each language has its own conventions regarding writing style, voice, and register. Translators must consider these factors to ensure the translated text matches the desired tone and style of the original. Adapting the writing style and tone while maintaining accuracy is essential for effective communication.

5. **Idiomatic Expressions:** Idiomatic expressions are common in scientific and technical texts, and translating them word-for-word can lead to confusion or loss of meaning. Translators must identify idiomatic expressions and find suitable equivalents or rephrase them to convey the intended meaning accurately in the target language.

CONCLUSION

Translation problems at the end of scientific and technical translations are a reality that translators frequently encounter. The role of terminological dictionaries in addressing these challenges cannot be overstated. Accurate and comprehensive terminological dictionaries that encompass contextual definitions, clarity on polysemy and homonymy, alternative equivalents, and up-to-date terminologies are indispensable assets for translators in the scientific and technical realms. By leveraging these resources, translators can enhance the precision and quality of their translations, ensuring effective communication across language barriers in these specialized fields.

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